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Modeling the impact of production and implementation modes on the business management system in the conditions of the innovative economy

Relevance of the research topic. *An important requirement of the modern innovative economy is the need to satisfy the unlimited needs of society in conditions of limited production potential and human resources. Increasingly, the methodology and tools for solving this problem are based on the use of a system of aggregated production functions – classical economic–mathematical or statistical modeling, which allows analyzing quantitative changes, correlations and ratios between various factors of production (human resources, own or borrowed capital, labor, land, innovative activity, scientific and technical progress) and the volume of products that can be produced by the subject of entrepreneurial activity under the condition of effective combination of entrepreneurial potential. However, taking into account modern trends, there is a need for uninterrupted research of the production system of the enterprise in order to adjust the management.*

Formulation of the problem. *Currently, there are a large number of production functions: Alain, Cobb–Douglas, Solow, Cobb–Douglas–Gray, Leontiev, Menkiu–Romer, Georgescu–Roeden, CES–function, LES–function. For our research, the Cobb–Douglas production function is of particular interest, which, by its logical construction, allows us to take into account asymmetric trends in variable production, the uneven distribution of business resources, and in this way ensure greater validity of forecasts. Therefore, the study of the specifics of the Cobb–Douglas production function, as well as the foundations of its construction, is an important problem today that needs analysis.*

Setting the goal and tasks of the research – *to determine the main directions of modeling the influence of production and implementation modes on the business management system in the conditions of the innovative economy.*

Research method or methodology. *The article uses the following methods: synthesis; modeling; abstraction; systematization and monographic generalization.*

Presentation of the main material. *Directions for modeling the influence of production and implementation modes on the business management system in the conditions of the innovative economy are proposed. Forecasting of the impact of factors on the dynamics of the volume of sales of economic entities over the last eleven years was determined based on the use of the Cobb–Douglas production function.*

Field of application of results. *The proposed modeling can be used by business entities for the purpose of diagnosing production activities and making timely management decisions.*

Conclusions according to the article. *Modeling of the influence of production and implementation modes on the business management system in the conditions of the innovative economy is proposed.*

Key words: *production function, forecasting, modeling, product realization, non–current assets, personnel, costs, entrepreneurship, economy, innovation, competitiveness*

Моделювання впливу виробничих та реалізаційних модусів на систему управління підприємництвом в умовах інноваційної економіки

Актуальність теми дослідження. Важливою вимогою сучасної інноваційної економіки є необхідність задоволення необмежених потреб суспільства в умовах обмеженості виробничого потенціалу та людських ресурсів. Усе частіше методологія та інструментарій вирішення цієї проблематики засновується на використанні системи агрегованих виробничих функцій – класичного економіко–математичного або статистичного моделювання, що дозволяє проаналізувати кількісні зміни, кореляцію та співвідношення між різноманітними чинниками виробництва (людськими ресурсами, власним або запозиченим капіталом, працею, землею, інноваційною діяльністю, науково–технічним прогресом) та обсягом продукції, що може бути вироблений суб'єктом підприємницької діяльності за умови ефективного поєднання підприємницького потенціалу. Однак з урахуванням сучасних тенденцій існує потреба безперервного дослідження системи виробництва підприємництва з метою корегування управління.

Постановка проблеми. У даний час існує велика кількість виробничих функцій: Алена, Кобба–Дугласа, Солоу, Кобба–Дугласа–Грея, Леонтьєва, Менк'ю–Ромера, Жеоржеску–Роедена, CES–функція, LES–функція. Для нашого дослідження особливий інтерес становить виробнича функція Кобба–Дугласа, яка за своєю логічною побудовою дозволяє враховувати асиметричні тенденції змінного виробництва, нерівномірність розподілу підприємницьких ресурсів і у такий спосіб забезпечити більшу валідність прогнозів. Отже дослідження специфіки виробничої функції Кобба–Дугласа, а також основ її побудови є важливою проблемою сьогодення, яка потребує аналізу.

Постановка мети і завдань дослідження – визначити основні напрямки моделювання впливу виробничих та реалізаційних модусів на систему управління підприємництвом в умовах інноваційної економіки.

Метод або методологія дослідження. В статті використано методи: синтезу; моделювання; абстрагування; систематизації й монографічного узагальнення.

Презентація основного матеріалу. Запропоновано напрями моделювання впливу виробничих та реалізаційних модусів на систему управління підприємництвом в умовах інноваційної економіки. Визначено прогнозування впливу чинників на динаміку обсягу реалізованої продукції суб'єктів господарювання за останні одинадцять років на основі використання виробничої функції Кобба–Дугласа.

Галузь застосування результатів. Запропоноване моделювання може використовуватися суб'єктами підприємницької діяльності з метою діагностики виробничої діяльності та прийняття вчасних управлінських рішень.

Висновки за статтею. Запропоновано моделювання впливу виробничих та реалізаційних модусів на систему управління підприємництвом в умовах інноваційної економіки.

Ключові слова: виробнича функція, прогнозування, моделювання, реалізація продукції, необоротні активи, персонал, витрати, підприємництво, економіка, інновації, конкурентоспроможність

Problem statement in general and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks. There is a need to review modern tools for modeling the impact of production and implementation modes on the business management system in the conditions of the innovative economy, taking into account modern conditions. This will allow you to make effective decisions in a timely manner and increase business profitability.

Analysis of the latest research and publications, which initiated the solution of this problem and on which the author relies, highlighting previously unsolved parts of the general problem, which is the subject of this article. In the writings of the scientists, the importance of studying the modeling of production activity in the conditions of the innovative economy is emphasized [1–3]. The authors define an adaptive toolkit that can be used for production

simulation [2–3]. However, there is a need to review the current state of management of business facilities taking into account current trends.

Formulation of the goals of the article – to determine the main directions of modeling the influence of production and implementation modes on the business management system in the conditions of the innovative economy.

Presentation of the main research material with full justification of the obtained scientific results. In

many cases, when studying the economic situation of an enterprise, the performance indicator is influenced by not one, but several factors. We suggest modeling the influence of production and sales modes on the business management system in the conditions of the innovative economy using the production indicators of the enterprise. We will conduct a study of the impact of personnel costs and the cost of non-current assets on the volume of sales (goods, services) of business entities (including

Table 1. Source data for the study of the impact of personnel costs and the cost of non-current assets on the volume of sales of business entities, using the Cobb–Douglas production function

Years	Total personnel costs, UAH mil., X_1	Non-current assets, total, UAH mil., X_2	The volume of sold products (goods, services) of business entities (including banks), total, UAH mil., Y
2010	263803,19	86855,41	3692554,479
2011	315382,31	105592,33	4302627,198
2012	374105,62	527960,03	4563794,768
2013	378223,21	2639813,17	4437326,06
2014	354424,90	2717620,35	4608978,077
2015	392558,13	3960148,88	5716431,039
2016	434790,14	4212813,14	6877077,356
2017	569937,37	4303282,79	8467031,958
2018	727110,09	4584315,56	10148847,23
2019	901245,25	4844512,94	10725442,97
2020	990589,16	5312301,38	11285578,87

Source: summarized by the authors using the state Internet–resource https://ukrstat.gov.ua/druk/publicat/kat_u/2018/zb/11/zd_2018.pdf

Figure 1. The sequence of stages of the study of the influence of factors on the dynamics using the Cobb–Douglas production function

Source: [1, p. 31]

banks) over the past eleven years using the Cobb–Douglas production function. The initial data for the processing of the production function and the study of the influence of production and sales modes on the performance indicator are presented in Table 1.

The research was conducted in three stages, the sequence of which is shown in Fig. 1 using Microsoft Excel spreadsheets and built–in functions.

The Cobb–Douglas production function – nonlinear multiple regression has the form:

$$Y = a_0 X_1^{a_1} X_2^{a_2} \quad (1)$$

At the first (preparatory) stage of the study, the specification of the Cobb–Douglas production function was carried out. For this purpose, by means of logarithmization and calculation of the corresponding differentials, this function was linearized, i.e. reduced to a linear form. For this, the built–in mathematical function LN was used (Fig. 2).

At the second (analytical) stage, we use the Microsoft Excel spreadsheet data analysis add–on to determine the parameters of the reduced linear regression (Fig. 3).

The quantitative impact (variation) of each of the two factors: personnel costs X_1 and the cost of non–current assets X_2 on the performance indicator: the volume of sold products (goods, services) of business entities (including banks) Y was determined. As a result of the calculations, the main sta-

tistical indicators and parameters of the reduced linear regression were obtained (Fig. 3). The given linear model of the volume of sold products has the form: $\ln(Y) = 4.15 + 0.85Z_1 + 0.03Z_2$. Parameters $a_0 = 4.15$; $a_1 = 0.85$ and $a_2 = 0.03$ are partial elasticity coefficients and indicate that with an increase in personnel costs by 1%, the volume of sold products will increase by 0.85%, and with an increase in the value of non–current assets by 1%, the effective indicator will increase by 0.03%. Parameter a_0 has no economic meaning. A total coefficient of determination of 0.96 was obtained. The general coefficient of determination indicates a close relationship between the selected factors and the indicator, and also that the variation in the volume of sold products by 95.73% is caused by the investigated factors introduced into the production model. Next, we use the given linear model to calculate the theoretical value of the volume of products sold and the point value of the forecast. The Cobb–Douglas production regression of the volume of output has the form: $Y = 63,493 + X_1^{0.85} + X_2^{0.03}$ (Fig 4.).

At the third (design) stage, we conduct an economic evaluation of the results of the regression analysis and recommendations for improving economic processes, in particular, the competitiveness of the products sold. Since $F_{\text{roz}} = 46610.73 > F_{\text{kp}} = 4.26$, it can be assumed with a reliability of $P = 0.95$ that the

Years	Total personnel costs, million hryvnias, X_1	Non-current assets, total, million hryvnias., X_2	Volume of sold products (goods, services) of business entities (including banks), total, million hryvnias., Y	Z_1	Z_2	Y_1	Y_{1r}	Y_r
2010	263803.19	86855.41	3692554	12.48	11.37	15.12	15.08	3547638.82
2011	315382.31	105592.33	4302627.198	12.66	11.57	15.27	15.24	4151564.78
2012	374105.62	527960.03	4563794.768	12.83	13.18	15.33	15.43	5001551.59
2013	378223.21	2639813.17	4437326.06	12.84	14.79	15.31	15.48	5258016.78
2014	354424.90	2717620.35	4608978.077	12.78	14.82	15.34	15.42	4978240.47
2015	392558.13	3960148.88	5716431.039	12.88	15.19	15.56	15.52	5483379.09
2016	434790.14	4212813.14	6877077.356	12.98	15.25	15.74	15.61	5991887.24
2017	569937.37	4303282.79	8467031.958	13.25	15.27	15.95	15.84	7551315.34
2018	727110.09	4584315.56	10148847.23	13.50	15.34	16.13	16.05	9309007.13
2019	901245.25	4844512.94	10725442.97	13.71	15.39	16.19	16.23	11194685.96
2020	990589.16	5312301.38	11285578.87	13.81	15.49	16.24	16.31	12162559.94

Figure 2. Specification of the Cobb–Douglas production function of the influence of personnel costs and the cost of non–current assets on the volume of sales of economic entities

Source: calculated by the authors

16	Summing up			Analysis of variance					
17		Regressive			df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
18	Multiple R	0.98		Regression	2	0.77	0.39	46610.73	0.00
19	R-squared	0.96		Remainder	8	0.00	0.00		
20	squared	0.95		Together	10	0.77			
21	error	660785577.76							
22	Observation	11							
23									
24		Coefficients	Standard error	t-statistic	P-Values	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95,0%	Upper 95,0%
25	Y-intersection	4.15	0.14	3.70	0.01	0.19	0.82	0.19	0.82
26	Variable X 1	0.85	0.05	4.19	0.00	0.10	0.34	0.10	0.34
27	Variable X 2	0.03	0.08	10.68	0.00	0.64	0.99	0.64	0.99
28									
29		Fkp= 4.26		tkp= 2.26					
30									
31	A linear model is presented	Ln(Y)=	4.15	+	0.85	Z ₁	+	0.03	Z ₂

Figure 3. The use of the "Data Analysis" add-on when studying the parameters of the linear regression of the volume of products sold of business entities, 2010–2020

Source: calculated by the authors

29		Fkp= 4.26		tkp= 2.26					
30									
31	A linear model is presented	Ln(Y)=	4.15	+	0.85	Z ₁	+	0.03	Z ₂
32									
33	Production regression	Y=	63.493	+	X ₁ ^{0,85}	+	X ₂ ^{0,03}		

Figure 4. View of the calculated Cobb–Douglas production regression of the volume of sold products of economic entities, 2010–2020

Source: calculated by the authors

adopted mathematical model is adequate to the experimental data and it is possible to forecast the volume of sales with its help. Since the t-statistics of the parameters a₀, a₁, and a₂ are 3.70, 4.19, and 10.68, respectively, which is greater than the critical value tkp=2.26. then with reliability P=0.95 it can be assumed that all parameters of the regression model are significant. The main parameters of the reduced linear regression are calculated step by step, they coincide with the coefficients found using the Data Analysis add-on (Fig. 5).

Marginal productivity of personnel costs for the forecast value of UAH 1,132,030.83 million. shows that with a change in personnel costs by UAH 1 million. the volume of sold products will change by UAH 10.38 million. at a constant amount of non-current assets. Marginal productivity of the value of

non-current assets for the forecast value of UAH 8105628.71 million. shows that when the value of non-current assets changes by 1 million hryvnias. the volume of sold products will change by 0.04 million hryvnias.. with unchanged personnel costs. For factors X₁ personnel costs 1132030.83 million hryvnias, X₂ value of non-current assets 8105628.71 million hryvnias. the forecast value of the indicator of the volume of sold products (goods, services) of business entities (including banks) was determined: UAH 1,377,803.60 million. (Fig. 6).

Since the total coefficient of elasticity A=a₁+a₂=0.85+0.03=0.88, with an increase in personnel costs and the cost of non-current assets by an average of 1.33 times, the volume of sold products (goods, services) sub of economic entities (including banks) will increase by 1.29 times. A

*Calculation of the confidence zone
the forecast value of the indicator*

The method of ordinary Jordan exclusions

	a_{01}	a_1	a_2	1
$0=$	11.00	143.73	157.65	-172.19
$0=$	143.73	1879.92	2064.75	-2251.68
$0=$	157.65	2064.75	2283.68	-2472.62
The first step:				
	0.00	a_1	a_2	1.00
$a_{01}=$	0.09	-13.07	-14.33	15.65
$0=$	13.07	1.92	4.79	-1.76
$0=$	14.33	4.79	24.13	-4.69
The second step:				
	0.00	0.00	a_2	1.00
$a_{01}=$	89.15	-6.82	18.29	3.69
$a_1=$	-6.82	0.52	-2.50	0.92
$0=$	-18.29	2.50	12.18	-0.31
The third step:				
	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00
$a_{01}=$	116.62	-10.57	1.50	4.15
$a_1=$	-10.57	1.03	-0.21	0.85
$a_2=$	1.50	-0.21	0.08	0.03

Оцінки параметрів приведеної лінійної регресії: a_{01} , a_1 та a_2

Figure 5. Calculation of the confidence zone of the forecast value of the volume of sold products (goods, services) of economic entities (including banks)

Source: calculated by the authors

I14 =EXP(H14)									
Research of the volume of products sold (goods, services) of business entities using Cobb-Douglas production regression									
1	Years	Total personnel costs, million hryvnias, X_1	Non-current assets, total, million hryvnias, X_2	Volume of sold products (goods, services) of business entities (including banks), total, million hryvnias, Y	Z_1	Z_2	Y_1	Y_{1r}	Y_r
2									
3	2010	263803.19	86855.41	3692554.479	12.48	11.37	15.12	15.08	3547638.82
4	2011	315382.31	105592.33	4302627.198	12.66	11.57	15.27	15.24	4151564.78
5	2012	374105.62	527960.03	4563794.768	12.83	13.18	15.33	15.43	5001551.59
6	2013	378223.21	2639813.17	4437326.06	12.84	14.79	15.31	15.48	5258016.78
7	2014	354424.90	2717620.35	4608978.077	12.78	14.82	15.34	15.42	4978240.47
8	2015	392558.13	3960148.88	5716431.039	12.88	15.19	15.56	15.52	5483379.09
9	2016	434790.14	4212813.14	6877077.356	12.98	15.25	15.74	15.61	5991887.24
10	2017	569937.37	4303282.79	8467031.958	13.25	15.27	15.95	15.84	7551315.34
11	2018	727110.09	4584315.56	10148847.23	13.50	15.34	16.13	16.05	9309007.13
12	2019	901245.25	4844512.94	10725442.97	13.71	15.39	16.19	16.23	11194685.96
13	2020	990589.16	5312301.38	11285578.87	13.81	15.49	16.24	16.31	12162559.94
14	2024	1132030.83	8105628.71	1	13.94	15.91	0.00		13774803.60

Figure 6. Results of processing and determination of the forecast value of the main influencing factors on the volume of sold products of economic entities, 2024

Source: calculated by the authors

table of values of the isoquant of the forecast value of the volume of sales, calculated values of the value of non-current assets, personnel costs and a graphic representation of their marginal productivity was created (Fig. 7).

Also, the actual, theoretical and forecast value of the volume of sold products (goods, services) of economic entities, 2010–2020, 2024, is graphically depicted using the Cobb–Douglas production regression $Y=63,493+ X_1^{0,85}+ X_2^{0,03}$ (Fig.8).

Figure 7. Calculation and graphical presentation of isoquant values for the forecast value of the volume of sold products (goods, services) of economic entities (including banks), 2024
 Source: calculated by the authors

Figure 8. Actual, theoretical and forecast value of the volume of products sold of economic entities, 2010–2020, 2024 using Cobb–Douglas production regression $Y=63,493+ X^{10,85}+ X^{20,03}$
 Source: calculated by the authors

Conclusions

So, the conducted research and forecasting of the influence of factors on the dynamics of the volume of sold products (goods, services) of economic entities over the last eleven years based on the use of the Cobb–Douglas production function showed that the selected factors have a positive effect on the competitiveness of the studied indicator, but all macroeconomic and microeconomic factors should be taken into account during further analysis and forecasting.

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